

CORRELATING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS WITH THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN GUMACA QUEZON

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Correlating Emotional Intelligence of Senior High School Learners with their Academic Performance in Gumaca Quezon

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Abstract

This study focused on correlating the emotional intelligence of senior high school learners with their academic performance in Gumaca, Quezon, S.Y. 2023-2024. This study involved 80 senior high school students. The findings show that the majority of the respondents, according to their age, are 17 years old and older. According to sex, which describes that most student respondents in senior high school are female, The academic performance of respondents is at the highest level, being outstanding. In terms of monthly income, the highest earners in every family are 5,000 below. The respondents are 40 grade 11 and grade 12 senior high school pupils. Forty seniors in grades 11 and 12 of senior high school are the responses. Based on the results of the personality test, senior high school students' emotional intelligence score is 41.72, which is considered high. The student respondents exhibit the largest percentage of emotional intelligence adaptation in their academic performance when studying. Number 9 has the highest mean of 4.89 and states that "I can motivate myself to learn and feel enjoyment, happiness, and pride to have better academic performance," while indicator number 3 "I can use it to guide me in my thoughts and actions" has the lowest rank with a mean of 3.98, interpreted as Much Agree (MA). This implies that the result of these needs is to improve the emotional intelligence of the students with the help and guidance of the teacher to guide their emotions, thoughts, and actions. Based on the results of this study, it was revealed that the average mean is very much in agreement, indicating that most of the senior high school respondents are adapting their emotional intelligence to improve their academic performance. In correlation, the relationship between emotional intelligence and the academic performance of the learners correlated significantly at 0.01 alpha (2 tailed) and 0.05 alpha (2 tailed). This factor showed a strong and positive correlation, concluding that emotional intelligence enhances students academic performance. Emotional intelligence is integrated into the curriculum and students' emotional needs are adequately managed to achieve this good impact. It suggests that developing emotional intelligence will boost students' academic achievement play a significant role in the learners' application of pleasant emotions throughout class.

Keywords: *academic performance, correlation, emotion, emotional intelligence, outstanding, personality test*

Introduction

Emotional Intelligence otherwise known as emotional quotient or EQ is the ability to understand, use and manage your emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate, effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and defuse conflict. Managing the emotional intelligence is the ability to build and maintain positive relationships. Develop relationship-building tactics with the other individual. Motivation is the drive that pushes us to make better choices for ourselves and succeed. It involves establishing goals, staying focused, and overcoming obstacles with perseverance. Acknowledge that increasing our emotional intelligence can improve our intellectual performance in the classroom. While some people are innately blessed with emotional intelligence, these talents may also be learned and improved with practice and self-awareness in day-to-day living. Emotional intelligence is built on a knowledge of oneself, including motives, emotions, and strengths and weaknesses. Understanding the value of self-awareness is necessary for this. This self-knowledge allows you to make better decisions and manage your emotions effectively to be successful.

Based on Tyagi and Gautam (2017) research, combine them to comprehend the information where emotional intelligence plays a crucial part in allowing people to experience emotions. People exhibit a variety of emotional traits, sentiments, and excitements during their daily lives.

When it comes to academic performance, research has revealed that emotional intelligence is almost as important as cognitive intelligence and having a conscientious attitude. This is because emotional intelligence of students is better equipped to deal with negative emotions that might disrupt learning.

The goal of this study is to help the students in their experience of academic performance by engaging them in various academic and non-academic activities such as extracurricular activities, assignment submission, interaction with other students, and class presence. Thus, lack of academic engagement in a classroom is a need to be addressed by mentioning their needs through describing low achievers who experienced boredom and eventually dropped out of their respective classes.

Based on the researcher's observations, some students are not aware of their emotional intelligence. They focus only on their intellectual qualities in their learning process. The researcher aims to see if the emotional intelligence has an impact on students learning in academic performance. The objective of the study is to find out the emotional intelligence have an effect on academic performance. The research proposal will investigate the effect of emotional intelligence (EI) on academic performance. Many psychologist researchers acknowledge the fact that emotions are core to learning and that teachers should understand their role during the learning

experience. Emotional Intelligence is imperative in academic performance yet it is not part of the school curriculum but need to practice it and balance to the Intelligence Quotient.

Research Questions

This research study aimed to determine the correlating emotional intelligence of Senior High School Grade 11 and 12 Students with their academic performance in Gumaca, Quezon for the SY 2023-2024. Specifically, this study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. academic performance;
 - 1.4. monthly income; and
 - 1.5. grade level?
2. What is the level of emotional intelligence of the learners?
3. What is the academic performance of the learners using emotional intelligence?
4. Is there any significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of the learners?
5. Based on the result what is the plan to sustain the academic performance of Senior High School learners using emotional intelligence?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design that aimed to systematically obtain information to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population. more specifically, correlating the emotional intelligence of Senior High School Learners with their academic performance in Gumaca, Quezon. The researcher used a survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's results, the researcher was able to determine the details of the study.

According to Shuttleworth 2019, as part of a scientific procedure known as descriptive research design, a subject's behavior is observed and described without any form of intervention.

Respondents

Quota Sampling was be utilized in this research: Quota sampling is a non-probability sampling method where researchers divide the population into exclusive subgroups and then sample a predetermined number of subjects from each subgroup to ensure representation of the overall population.

Eighty (80) students officially enrolled at Eastern Quezon College Inc. located at Gumaca Quezon were selected through Quota Sampling.

According to Simkus, (2023) Quota sampling is a non-probability sampling method where the researcher will assign quotas to group of people in order to create subgroups of individuals that represent characteristics of the target population as a whole. Some example of these characteristics are gender, sex, residency, education level, or income. Once the subgroup are formed, the researchers used their own judgement to select the subjects from each segment to produce the final sample.

Instrument

The researcher prepared a research-made questionnaire which was be validated by two experts.

Part I. of the questionnaire includes the profile of the respondents. Part II is the level of emotional intelligence of the learners using the likert scale of; Very Much Agree (VMA) 5, Much Agree (MA) 4, Agree (MA) 3, Less Agree (LA) 2, and Least Agree (LEA) correlating emotional intelligence of Senior High School Learners with their academic performance in Gumaca, Quezon.

A pilot testing was be conducted to twelve (12) respondents from a school which is not a target of the study using Cronbach's Alpha. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of internal consistency of the research instrument. If the result is 0.70 and above there is an internal consistency of the instrument and it is acceptable.

Procedure

After Pilot Testing. Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the schools Principal and Adviser. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used the time allotted for vacant time to avoid distraction of class discussion. The student response was given enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher collected them for tallying the scores and to applied the statistical treatment used in the study.

The descriptive research design method using like scale was used in order to rate correlating emotional intelligence of senior high school students. Data were gathered through “Quota Sampling” both male and female officially enrolled in the private school in Gumaca, Quezon was be selected to fill the questionnaire. Data was be gathered through face-to-face survey following the safety health protocols to prevent the spread of the virus.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for analysis. They were tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency was were to interpret the profile of the respondents. To test the significant relationship involving ordinal variables, the researcher used the Spearman’s Rho correlation.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretation. The first part is described the profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Sex, Academic Performance (2nd Quarter), Monthly Income, Grade Level and Emotional Intelligence bar. The second part is the level of emotional intelligence of the learners. The third part are the academic performance of the learners using emotional intelligence. The fourth part Significant Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of the Learners.

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

Age	Frequency(<i>f</i>)	Percentage(%)	Rank
15-16 years old	32	40	2
17 years old and above	48	60	1
Total	80	100	

Table 1 presents the distribution of the age of the respondents which illustrates that the ages 17 years old and above has the highest ranking with a frequency of 48 or 60 %, while 15-16 years old has the lowest percentage with the frequency of 32 or 40%. These findings suggest that senior students exhibit a high level of engagement with emotional intelligence. It is evident that older students apply their emotional intelligence in a responsible and conscientious way. This underscores the necessity for age-appropriate emotional intelligence support and instruction within senior high school curricula. The significant correlation between age and students' emotional intelligence engagement highlights this need.

According to the DepEd 2022 guidelines, the Senior High School age range in the K–12 curriculum is 17 years and older, which aligns perfectly with the ages of the respondents.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

Sex	Frequency(<i>f</i>)	Percentage(%)	Rank
Male	37	46	2
Female	43	54	1
Total	80	100	

Based on the statistics shown in Table 2, the proportion of female respondents is 54% (43 out of 80) and the male respondents is 46% (37 out of 80). The research implies that female students may naturally or socially lean more toward emotional intelligence, given the higher proportion of female respondents and their engagement in emotional intelligence. This demonstrates the necessity of gender-sensitive methods in the learning process of the students which have an impact in their emotional intelligence, guarantee that male and female students receive the same encouragement and support in order to acquire these vital abilities in their emotional intelligences in academic performance.

Bailey's (2020) study explores the relationships between gender and academic performance in the classroom which can see the most affected of emotional intelligence are the academic performance. According to the study, female students constitute the majority in terms of classroom participation. This higher participation rate among female students is significantly associated with better final course grades, suggesting a positive correlation between participation and academic performance. However, Bailey cautions that this correlation might be influenced by the composition of the classroom.

Implication

In particular, courses with a larger proportion of female students typically receive better average scores for their academic achievement in the classroom as well as greater overall participation rates in their academic performance at school. This begs the question of whether the observed link is mostly attributable to the higher levels of involvement exhibited by female students or to the supportive learning environment that may be more common in classes with a female majority.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Academic Performance (2nd Quarter)*

<i>Academic Performance (2nd Quarter)</i>	<i>Frequency(f)</i>	<i>Percentage(%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
90-100 (Outstanding)	61	76	1
85-89 (Very Satisfactory)	16	20	2
80 - 84 (Satisfactory)	3	4	3
75 - 79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	0	0	4.5
Below 75 (Did Not Meet Expectation)	0	0	4.5
Total	80	100	

Based on their academic achievement during the second quarter, respondents are distributed in detail in Table 3. The 61 responders out of 80 or 76% of the sample, received an academic performance rating of 90–100 (Outstanding), according to the data presented. However, the lowest frequency is seen in the 80–84 (satisfactory) group, where there have 3 responses or 4% of the sample based from the responds of the students in Senior High School.

Johnston (2024) claims that pupils who advance by utilizing the highest emotional intelligence levels have the most impact on their grades and perform exceptionally well in school. These pupils make use of self-awareness to pinpoint their advantages.

Implication

The association between senior high school students' academic performance and emotional intelligence is significantly affected by these findings in a number of ways. High academic achievement and emotional intelligence of the learners are significantly correlated among senior high school students. In order to promote both academic and personal development, this emphasizes how crucial it is to include emotional intelligence instruction in the curriculum which need to be improve and enhance more the academic of the students in their learning process. Schools may support every student in realizing their full potential by emphasizing their overall development through identifying in what level they have in their own emotional intelligence.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Monthly Income*

<i>Monthly Income</i>	<i>Frequency(f)</i>	<i>Percentage(%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
20,000 - Above	16	20	3
15,000 - 19,999	14	18	4
10,000 - 14,000	13	16	5
5,000 - 9,999	17	21	2
Below 5,000	20	25	1
Total	80	100	

Table 4 presents the distribution of the respondents according to monthly income has below 5,000 the highest ranking with a frequency of 20 or 25%, while 10,000-14,000 monthly has the lowest percentage with a frequency of 13 or 16%. These results pointed that the monthly income of every family have big amount suitable in their schooling to have good school of choice. The significant role that economic factors play in educational opportunities and outcomes. Ensuring that all students, regardless of their family's income level, have access to quality education and support systems is essential for fostering academic success and emotional well-being. By addressing these disparities, schools and policymakers can work towards creating a more equitable and inclusive educational landscape.

As explained by Luella (2015), the total population's income of ₱5,000 for Norms Families was grouped and ranked into per capita income deciles. This method involves dividing the population into ten equal groups based on their income levels, with each decile representing 10% of the population.

Implication

By organizing income data in this way, researchers and policymakers can analyze how income distribution varies across different segments of the population. This approach helps to identify disparities in income distribution and assess the economic well-being of various demographic groups within the population.

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Grade Level*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Frequency(f)</i>	<i>Percentage(%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
11	40	50	0.5
12	40	50	0.5
Total	80	100	

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents according to grade level, showing that each grade level has the same percentage and frequency. This uniform distribution suggests that the study sample is evenly distributed across different grade levels within Senior High School. The equal distribution of respondents across grade levels in Table 4 suggests that emotional intelligence is a significant

factor influencing academic performance throughout senior high school. This uniform representation highlights the need for consistent and comprehensive emotional intelligence education and support across all grade levels, ensuring that every student has the opportunity to develop these essential skills.

Moreover, research in 2015 by Rivers and Brackett explored how emotional intelligence interventions could be effectively implemented in schools to cultivate EI skills among students. Their findings suggested that structured EI programs not only improve academic performance but also contribute to a positive school climate, fostering emotional well-being and interpersonal relationships.

Implication

This aligns with the advocacy for comprehensive emotional intelligence education across all grade levels, ensuring that students receive continuous support in developing crucial skills like self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management.

Part II. The Level of Emotional Intelligence of the Learners.

Table 6. Respondents assessment on the Level of Emotional Intelligence of Senior High School Learners

No.	Component of Emotional Intelligence	Yes	No
1	I overcome difficulties by moving step by step.	78	2
2	I find it hard to enjoy life.	11	69
3	I prefer work that I am told what to do.	69	11
4	I know how to handle upsetting situation.	71	9
5	I like every person I meet.	62	18
6	I try to make my life as meaningful as possible.	70	10
7	I can express my feelings easily.	77	3
8	I attempt to see things as they are without exaggerating.	67	13
9	I control my emotions.	75	5
10	I am always sure of myself.	74	6
11	I think something is wrong with my mind.	40	40
12	I cannot show affection.	41	39
13	I cannot control my anger.	7	73
14	I cannot begin new things.	9	71
15	I like collecting information when faced with difficult situation.	72	8
16	I like assisting people.	9	71
17	I cannot smile easily.	7	73
18	I cannot understand other people's feelings.	8	72
19	I rely on other people's ideas more than mine.	7	73
20	I believe that I can be the best.	74	6
21	I do not know what I can do best.	7	73
22	I cannot express my ideas to others.	12	68
23	I cannot share my feelings with others.	9	71
24	I do not have self confidence.	5	75
25	I have lost my mind.	9	71
26	I am always optimistic.	69	11
27	It is hard for me to make adjustment.	68	12
28	I like knowing about a problem before solving it.	69	11
29	It is hard for me to stop talking once I start.	75	5
30	I always take advantage of people.	50	30
31	I am cheerful.	75	5
32	I prefer other people to make decision and not me.	17	63
33	I can handle stress with ease.	70	10
34	I have good feelings about everyone.	80	0
35	I respect others.	80	0
36	I am impulsive.	11	69
37	I always do so weird things.	40	40
38	I always cling to others.	75	5
39	I believe that I can handle upsetting situations.	41	39
40	I always feel embarrassed when doing anything.	10	70
41	Other people think I am not assertive.	20	60
42	People think I am not sociable.	11	69
43	I like having fun.	78	2
44	I always get anxious.	6	74
45	I don't keep friends.	11	69
46	I feel good about myself despite the negatives and the positive points.	68	12
47	If someone force me to leave my home, I will not adjust.	40	40
48	I usually feel that I will fail before beginning something new.	11	69

49	I don't like hurting other people feelings.	19	61
50	I cannot keep things in the right way.	22	58
Total		2,086	1,914

Weighted Average Mean = 41.72 High Emotional Intelligence
 Legend: "Low Emotional Intelligence (0 - 10), Below Average Emotional Intelligence (11 - 20), Average Emotional Intelligence (21-30), Above Average Emotional Intelligence (31 - 40), High Emotional Intelligence (41 - 50)"

Table 6 shows the emotional intelligence bar with a total average mean of 41.72 interpreted as High Emotional Intelligence. It shows that having emotional intelligence can help students improve in their studies at school. Adapting emotional intelligence in themselves helps maintain good academic performance inside the classroom.

As stated by Lucila O. Bance and John Ray B. Acorpio (2016), a student who possesses emotional-social intelligence is capable of performing academically in a class or field they belong in and is also able to effectively demonstrate it through empathetic and sympathetic behavior. This study has received support from other people to the extent that their interactions with it can benefit their societal interactions and other environmental determinants.

Part III. The Academic Performance of the Learners Using Emotional Intelligence.

Table 7. Mean and Interpretation on Academic Performance of the Learners using Emotional Intelligence of Senior High School Learners

Applying Emotional Intelligence, I can...		Mean	Int.	Rank
1.	communicate better.	4.6	VMA	4
2.	help me in achieving academic success.	4.59	VMA	6
3.	use to guide me in my thoughts and actions.	3.98	MA	10
4.	enhance my creativity to try new things and share my ideas.	4.54	VMA	7
5.	concentrate and develop strategies to cope with challenge in studying.	4.86	VMA	2
6.	improve my decision making, critical thinking that helps me solve problems easily.	4.73	VMA	3
7.	check on my emotions better and be emphatic to others around me.	4.31	VMA	8
8.	can maintain emotional balance that enhances my thinking and decision making.	4.29	VMA	9
9.	motivate myself to learn and feel enjoyment, happiness and pride to have better academic performance.	4.89	VMA	1
10.	manage my feelings appropriately and effectively, which enables me to participate to achieve a common grade.	4.78	VMA	5
Average Weighted Mean		4.66	VMA	

Legend: "Least Agree (1.0 - 1.80), Less Agree (1.81 - 2.60), Agree (2.61 - 3.40), Much Agree (3.41 - 4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21 - 5.0)".

Table 7 presents highlight that students highly value self-motivation and positive emotional experiences as crucial for academic success, as indicated by the highest mean score of 4.89 for indicator 9. Conversely, indicator 3's lower mean score of 3.98 suggests there is room for improvement in students' ability to effectively use emotions to guide their thoughts and actions. The general weighted mean of 4.66 across all indicators indicates strong agreement among students regarding the importance of emotional intelligence in their academic journey, emphasizing the critical role teachers play in fostering and sustaining EI through guidance and support. This underscores the need for educators to implement strategies that cultivate emotional intelligence skills, ensuring students can effectively manage their emotions and enhance their academic performance.

With increased awareness in its potential to inspire people to learn and perform better academically, emotional intelligence (EI) has become a crucial component of academic achievement. This review attempts to provide light on the mechanisms via which emotional intelligence influences learning experiences and accomplishments by synthesizing the body of research on the relationship between academic outcomes, self-motivation, and emotional intelligence according to Doe (2023).

In order to help people think and act in ways that will lead to desired results, emotional intelligence (EI) provides a framework for comprehending and controlling emotions. This review provides insights into how emotional intelligence (EI) concepts might inform various elements of personal and professional life by examining the literature that has been written about the application of EI as a guide for behavior and decision-making. John Smith (2023).

Implication

To effectively enhance students' emotional intelligence, educators should integrate emotional intelligence training into the curriculum and create a supportive classroom environment that encourages open discussions about emotions. Organizing skill-building workshops and using role-playing exercises can provide students with practical tools for emotional regulation and empathy. Additionally, investing in teacher training will equip educators to effectively teach and model these essential skills, ultimately improving students' academic performance and overall well-being.

Part IV. Significant Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of the Learners

Table shows the study found out that the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of the learners correlated significantly at 0.01 alpha (2 tailed) and 0.05 alpha (2 tailed). Based on the gathered data there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between academic performance of the learners. As shown with the given

data, emotional intelligence were correlated with the academic performance of the learners.

Table 8. Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of Senior High School Learners

Variables	df	Spearman p-value	t - value	p- value	Significant Level	Decision
Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of Senior High School Learners	79	0.221	0.16199897371	0.01	0.05	Reject Ho

Legend: "No or negligible relationship (0.01 - 0.19), Weak Relationship (0.20 - 0.29), Moderate Relationship (0.30 - 0.39), Strong Relationship (0.40 - 0.69), Very Strong Relationship (> 0.70)".

It conforms to the study of Pandey (2019), demonstrated a strong and positive correlation between each of the emotional intelligence factors, which ultimately led to the conclusion that emotional intelligence has a positive impact on students' academic performance by engaging school curriculum through the proper handling of students emotional intelligence.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

The respondents' ages fell within the typical bracket of senior high school students in the Philippine education system, with a gender distribution skewed towards female respondents. Academic performance predominantly achieved outstanding ratings. The most of the respondent belong to the bracket of monthly income is 5,000 below. The grade level of respondents are equally 40 of Grade 11 and 12.

The average emotional intelligence score highlights its crucial benefits for students' academic success. Developing emotional intelligence helps students navigate challenges, adapt well, and achieve sustained academic success.

Using emotional intelligence helps students engage effectively with their studies and enjoy the learning process. It fosters a positive impact toward learning, increases motivation, and improves academic performance.

There is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of the learners.

As a result of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following;

To the School Administrators, they may help to design a guidance program for teachers focusing on emotional intelligence to sustain the academic performance of learners.

To the parents, it may help as basis in determining the level contributing of emotional intelligence on their children on how to manage it properly to sustain the needs of the children..

To the Teachers, they may help them to monitor the emotional intelligence of the students on the day to day activity to sustain the academic performance.

To the Students, they may help them to know their level, they can grow in emotional wisdom and expand their emotional intelligence with awareness.

To the Future Researchers, it will serve as guide and future reference as they conduct the same research topics and explore strategies for boosting emotional intelligence, thereby providing targeted interventions to foster emotional growth and self-awareness.

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